

SME Growth and PPP Business Models webinars content

D2.7 version 2.3

May 2018

merlin

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780.460

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MERLIN

Methodologies for Researcher
Led INnovations

GA No. 780.460

ICT-32-2017 EU H2020

Confidentiality Level: PU

Document Type	Contract Deliverable	
Document & WP No.	D2.7	WP2
Document Title	“SME Growth” and “PPP Business Models” webinars content	
Release date	Version 2.3 - 31/05/2018	

Executive summary

This document, D2.7 — PPP webinars – is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020".

Merlin aims to foster and accelerate the transfer of knowledge from the projects funded in FP7 and H2020, be it on the form of license agreement, patent or ideally, spinoff or startup to directly exploit them, by organising practical hands-on workshops; meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors; and by attending scientific conferences to reach a wider public. The programme will equip participants with knowledge, skills and a network to generate market-led business models to unlock potential and accelerate this journey.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide the initial content and teaching materials of the 4 webinars SME Growth and PPP Business Models that will be delivered in September and December 2018 and September and November 2019. In addition, prior to the execution of the webinars, attendees will be surveyed by project participants in order to provide greater options for discussion points during the events and will receive content in advance to prepare fully for a more topic-specific and interactive experience.

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Document Control Page			
Title	"SME Growth" and "PPP Business Models" webinars content		
Creator	SJIC and CIV		
Description	Description of the content used in the SME Growth and PPP webinars, with focus on photonics and 5G		
Review status	Action	Person/Partner	Date
	Completed by WP Leader	Indrė Laurinčiukaitė/ CIV	28/05/2018
	Approved by Peer Panel	Kirsten Masson / SJIC	30/05/2018
	Approved by QA	Diego Alonso / UPCT	31/05/2018
Distribution	Confidential		PU

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	19/05/2018	Dovilė Motuzaitė	First version of the deliverable PPP.
1.2	23/05/2018	Indrė Laurinčiukaitė	Second version of the deliverable PPP.
1.4	21/05/2018	Kirsten Masson	First version of the deliverable SME.
1.8	25/05/2018	Kirsten Masson	Second version of the deliverable SME.
2.3	31/05/2018	Diego Alonso	Final version of both webinars.

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1. Introduction

This document, D2.7 — public-private partnership (PPP) workshop content (PPPC)— is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020"¹ and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020". The purpose is to provide a description of the material that will be used in the four webinars which are SME Growth – Access to Finance, SME Growth – The Commercialisation Journey, PPP in 5G and PPP in Photonics.

Funding in ICT project under FP7 and H2020 totals over 11.000 million € by the end of the current work programme. Stimulated and supported by these programs, many researchers in universities, institutes and SMEs have worked hard on developing new ground breaking technologies and disruptive services. But when it comes to commercialize the results or create a company, these researchers are unsure on how to proceed. MERLIN project, funded in the context of the EC initiative *Innovation Radar*, wants to start changing this situation by organizing a set of activities aiming:

- To stimulate a greater interest in the scientific community to view their research results as potential opportunities to be exploited with the correct business model.
- To equip researchers with modern, need-first and market-led methodologies that will help them to shape their ideas and outputs into innovations to be ready for market validation and posterior commercialization.
- To introduce the rich European entrepreneurship ecosystem and the opportunities it offers to create and support startups on their journey.

Among the planned activities, it is worth highlighting the following:

- Organisation 45 practical workshops covering state-of-the-art innovation and entrepreneurship methodologies in 8 European cities.
- Organisation of 5 workshops in scientific conferences to reach more researchers and engage them with the activities organized by MERLIN and other ICT-32 projects.
- Organisation of 8 meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors by the end of each year.
- Organisation of 4 webinars on SME growth and new business models for public-private partnership.

This document provides the description of the content used for the 4 webinars. It describes the theory to be presented during the webinars as well case studies to demonstrate the learnings. In addition, prior to the execution of the webinars, attendees will be surveyed by project participants in order to provide greater options for discussion points during the events and will receive content in advance to prepare fully for a more topic-specific and interactive experience. In addition, relevant links to further reading will be included to ensure the participants are well equipped to implement the learnings into their own practice.

1.1. Audience

The main intended audience for this document is the MERLIN project consortium and the European Commission. The audience of the webinars are researchers and startups from the photonics and 5G fields, respectively to the topic of the webinar. This deliverable will be made public, as well as the recording of the webinars. The target audience of the webinars are researchers and startups from the ICT field.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

1.2. Structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 provides general information about the webinar structure
- Section 3 presents the theory and examples on PPPs, which are common to both webinars on Photonics and 5G
- Section 4 describes the content for the webinar on Photonics
- Section 5 describes the content for the webinar on 5G
- Section 6 describes the content for the webinar on SME Growth- Access to Finance
- Section 7 describes the content for the webinar on SME Growth- The Commercialisation Journey
- Section 8 draws conclusions.

2. General information about the webinars

Duration of the webinars: Approximately 1 hour with 15 minutes for questions

Optimal number of participants: Approximately 40, but number is unlimited online

Target groups: Junior and senior researchers, PhD students on their last years and post-doc with research results

The main requirements for the webinar:

We are assessing webinar platforms and it is likely that Webinar platform GoToMeeting or Youtube will be used.

- A quiet room will be required.
- Renowned experts in the webinar topics will present some webinar content (ie SME Growth).
- Questionnaire responses from workshop participants will be reviewed to determine relevant feedback for further webinar enhancement.
- The webinar will be set up as an event so that participants can register and sign in details can be provided.
- Slides will be on screen so all participants can view
- A producer will be required to manage Q&A session, as well as any technical issues which may arise

Agenda of the webinar:

- Attendees will be surveyed by project participants in order to provide greater options for discussion points during the events and will receive content in advance to prepare fully for a more topic-specific and interactive experience.
- Hosting partner will moderate the webinar, introducing the speaker/s, making a short introduction of the MERLIN project, underlying the goals of the project and its scope, as well as introducing the learning objectives of the webinar, general rules and. He/she will also conduct the Q&A session.
- Invited speaker/s will deliver the content of the webinar and answer questions.
- Hosting partner will close the webinar.

Webinars will be recorded and hosted online on the project Youtube channel. Also, Q&A session will be processed and the most interesting questions/answers will be transcribed and made available online on the

project website. The “SME Growth” webinars will be present by David Gill and Uday Phadke, but the invited speakers for the PPPs have not already been decided.

3. Public-Private Partnerships

This section describes the theory on PPP itself. This theory is explained during both webinars in order to get the participants on the same level in terms on what PPPs actually are.

3.1. What is PPP

A public-private partnership (PPP) is a very particular type of contract whereby the public partner (government entity) delegates some of its own responsibilities to a private partner under a long-term contract that defines the rights and obligations of each party during the term as well as the mechanisms for its financial re-equilibrium arising from unforeseen events or lack of compliance of the parties.

Public-private partnerships between a government agency and private-sector company can be used to finance, build and operate projects, such as public transportation networks, parks and convention centers. Financing a project through a public-private partnership can allow a project to be completed sooner or make it a possibility in the first place.

In short, a PPP is a contractual agreement between a public agency and a private sector entity, through which skills and assets of each sector are shared in delivering a service or a facility for the use of the general public.

Figure 1 Public-private partnership

Public-private partnerships are typically found in transport infrastructure such as highways, airports, railroads, bridges and tunnels. Municipal and environmental infrastructure include water and wastewater facilities. Public service accommodations include school buildings, prisons, student dormitories and entertainment or sports facilities. Figure 2 represents an example of a three-way relationship between the government, the private sector and the community when building affordable housing.

Figure 2 PPP: three-way relationship example

The residents/community are in need of affordable housing. The government decides to build the houses for the community. Since the government's primary job does not include doing construction work, they decide to do a PPP with a private business in order to complete the project. The private sector has the capabilities to do the construction work, they receive funding from the government for the project and develop the housing and after the project is done they are responsible for maintaining it. In case there is a need for new regulations to be put into place in order to build the affordable housing, the government has the capabilities to do so.

PPPs always take place in the arena of the political economy because the parties contracting are not equal. One party is a government/public entity, and the other one is a private entity. Governments change and so do policies. And in countries where the rule of law is not enough established to maintain the stability of the contract, investors see a significant political risk that will need to be mitigated. This applies to termination of contracts but also to payment risks. A main risk is the regulatory one, e.g., the commitment of government to comply with a tariff law. Adjustment of tariffs can be highly political, particularly in electoral years, and therefore a private project can be easily politicized. Investors seek protection against such risks through guarantees, sometimes backed by a multilateral, international arbitration for dispute resolution and higher returns on equity.

PPPs require a lot of business developer skills which need to be interdisciplinary, often drawing in people with expertise in finance, economics, law, engineering, environment, accounting/taxes or other fields. Projects move ahead slowly, first to establish sound engineering and economics, then financial and legal feasibility, and finally political will to insert private-sector participation. Private-sector participation typically introduces new governance rules in a sector, externalizing costs or processes hidden until then. These projects can therefore awake unions or specific interest groups and rapidly become very politicized. A political champion is critical. It might be a key minister. In certain countries, it requires firm commitment of the president of the country. It has to be someone who can bring the stakeholders along and has the power to make decisions. Another critical key for success is the speed of a project since they need to be structured and awarded within a political cycle—and those are quite short, since governments change every four or five years.

3.2. PPP development stages

A PPP is a long term project which requires a thorough planning beforehand, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 PPP development stages

The project process can be split into 4 phases:

- **Phase 1.** Strategic planning, project pre-feasibility, PPP suitability testing, internal clearance and other similar tasks are performed in order to set the PPP scene – the current situation of the market/problem at hand. This phase is used to identify the problem, market, risks, opportunities and other objects.
- **Phase 2.** Full feasibility study, PPP preparation and clearance is conducted. The plan is finalized and the process is ready to be implemented.
- **Phase 3.** The final approval is given and the project is awarded to the company which provided the best plan. Procurement for the project is started. Phase 2 and Phase 3 together are called the *PPP development pipeline*.
- **Phase 4.** The project is being implemented and the project activities are overseen and monitored.

3.3. PPP examples

PPPs can be implemented in a variety of fields, as illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4 PPP examples

As mentioned beforehand, PPPs are typically found in transport infrastructure such as highways, airports, railroads, bridges and tunnels, water and wastewater facilities and other important infrastructure used by the public. However, a PPP can be initiated in order to develop other objects and technologies – governments are encouraging the private sector to develop new technologies in health, ICT and other sectors by providing subsidies and financing such R&D projects. The purpose of these projects is to encourage the scientists and other professionals to develop technologies that would later implemented and improve the public's livelihood.

3.4. PPPs in the context of the European Commission and Work Programmes

The European Commission has been investing heavily in Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) to enable a long-term, strategic approach to research and innovation and reduce uncertainties by allowing for long-term commitments. The objective is to provide the framework that allows companies and member states to focus on key technologies and their implementation through federated projects. More than € 20 billion are planned to be invested in the 5 coming years in the context of the Digital Single Market.

There are two types of PPP actions (see Figure 5), contractual and institutional PPPs.

- **Contractual PPPs** are a structured collaboration between the European Commission and private actors to provide input to work programmes to ensure that calls for proposals are relevant and targeted towards industry. Over time, the cPPPs have been granted a large portion of the Horizon 2020 budget, and they are a good opportunity to take part in to gain access to large-scale, industry-driven, EU-funded projects. The Commission is the only public partner in a cPPP, and the authorities in the participating countries do not contribute. The first cPPPs were launched in 2009, and later on they became incorporated more closely into the framework programme H2020. Calls for proposals are primarily issued by cPPPs under Pillar 2: Industrial Leadership. The following cPPPs active under Horizon 2020:
 - Energy-efficient Buildings (EeB)
 - European Green Vehicles Initiative (EGVI)
 - Sustainable Process Industry (SPIRE)
 - Robotics (SPARC)
 - Photonics
 - High Performance Computing (HPC)
 - 5G Infrastructure (5G)
 - Big Data Value
- **Institutional PPPs** are regulated under Article 187 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). They generally take the form of Joint Technology Initiatives (JTIs) or Joint Undertakings (JU), which aim is to take a long-term strategic approach to research and innovation; provide a legal framework for bringing together key actors; make EU funding more effective by sharing resources, funding and infrastructure; promote cross-sectoral collaboration; develop an internal market for innovative solutions; and bring innovative solutions to the market more rapidly. Calls are issued under Pillar 2: Industrial Leadership. The following iPPPs have been established and are currently active under Horizon 2020:
 - ARTEMIS (integrated ICT systems)
 - ENIAC (nanoelectronics)

- Clean Sky 2 (aviation technology)
- Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2
- Innovative Medicines 2
- Single European Sky ATM Research (SESAR) (air traffic management system)
- Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership (ECSEL)
- Shift2Rail
- Bio-based Industries (BBI)

Figure 5 PPPs and the European Commission

3.5. PPP benefits

PPPs provide many benefits, some of which include:

- Provide a legal structure to pool resources and to gather critical mass.
- Make research and innovation funding across the EU more efficient by sharing financial, human and infrastructure resources.
- Facilitate the creation of an internal market for innovative products and services.
- Enable innovative technologies to get faster to the market.
- Can provide the right framework for international companies to anchor their research and innovation investments in Europe.
- Enable the scale of research and innovation effort needed to address critical societal challenges and major EU policy objectives.

Such projects can provide not only new facilities to the public, but encourage the scientific community to develop new technologies that would later be implemented in real life.

Figure 6 Benefits of PPPs

3.6. PPP drawbacks

Even though PPPs provide the public with better services and facilities, such projects have some downsides as well:

- **Project risks.** Even though the best private partners are chosen for each project, the project still bears risks. For example, there may be some unforeseen forces that might interrupt the project or increase the chances of the project failing.
- **Private partner bears risk.** Every public-private partnership involves risks for the private participant, which reasonably expects to be compensated for accepting those risks. This can increase government costs.
- **Limitations on cost-effectiveness.** When there are only a limited number of private entities that can perform these tasks, such as with the development of a jet fighter, the limited number of private participants that are big enough to take these tasks on might limit the competitiveness required for cost-effective partnering.
- **Project profits depend on many variables.** Profits of the projects can vary depending on the assumed risk, competitive level, complexity, and the volume of the project being performed.
- **Cost assessment risks.** If the expertise in the partnership lies heavily on the private side, the government is at an inherent disadvantage. For example, it might be unable to accurately assess the proposed costs.

In order to mitigate such drawbacks, extensive planning and collaboration is key to the success of the project.

Figure 7 Drawbacks of PPPs

Project profits depend on many variables

Cost assessment risks

4. Photonics

This section describes the photonics market and provides an insight into the world of successful photonics PPP projects.

4.1. What is photonics

Photonics is the science of light. It is the technology of generating, controlling, and detecting light waves and photons, which are particles of light. The characteristics of the waves and photons can be used to explore the universe, cure diseases, and even to solve crimes. Scientists have been studying light for hundreds of years. The colors of the rainbow are only a small part of the entire light wave range, called the electromagnetic spectrum. Photonics explores a wider variety of wavelengths, from gamma rays to radio, including X-rays, UV and infrared light.

According to report², the global market for Photonics products accounted for a volume of EUR 445 billion in 2015, with Europe having a 15% of the share. Some more details, extracted from a report from Photonics21³ PPP, are provided in the slides.

Figure 8 Photonics Market

² Photonics economic impact study. First Periodic Report, EuroPho21 (project no. 643995)

³ Market Research Study Key Data, Photonics 2017

4.2. Photonics application in real life

Even if we cannot see the entire electromagnetic spectrum, visible and invisible light waves are a part of our everyday life. Photonics is everywhere: in consumer electronics (barcode scanners, DVD players, remote TV control), telecommunications (internet), health (eye surgery, medical instruments), manufacturing industry (laser cutting and machining), defense and security (infrared camera, remote sensing), entertainment (holography, laser shows) and other industries and technologies.

Figure 9 Some of the industries that implement photonics

4.3. Photonics PPP

The European Technology Platform Photonics21 represents the photonics community of industry and research organisations. Jointly with the European Commission our members develop and implement a common photonics strategy in a Horizon2020 Public Private Partnership (PPP) to spur growth and jobs in Europe. Photonics21 unites the majority of the leading photonics industries and relevant R&D stakeholders along the whole economic value chain throughout Europe. Today Photonics21 has more than 2500 members.

Photonics21 aims to establish Europe as a leader in the development and deployment of photonics technologies within the various applications fields such as ICT, lighting, industrial manufacturing, life science, safety as well as in education and training. The ETP Photonics21 coordinates photonics research and innovation priorities and provides input to the European research framework programme Horizon 2020.

Figure 10 Photonics PPP – Photonics21

4.4. Photonics PPP case study #1 – CHEQUERS

The first photonics PPP example includes CHEQUERS. The project aims to develop a compact high performance laser sensor to detect harmful substances in war struck areas and in terrorist-affected areas. This device is able to detect and identify hazardous chemicals and compounds quickly, easily and at significant range in war-struck areas or areas of terrorist attacks.

Innovation relies on the device’s ability to detect and identify multiple target molecular compounds while maintaining high sensitivity, speed, low cost, ease of use and portability.

The project received funding from European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program.

The project is being developed by:

- Non-profit intermediary operating in the market space between business and academia, laser manufacturer,
- Research institutes in Germany and the UK,
- Private SME which commercialize the research effort of the founder in the field of optoelectronics,
- The Federal Criminal Police Office of Germany.

Since the consortium involves private and public sectors, the application of the final product is ensured

Figure 11 Photonics PPP – Chequers

4.5. Photonics PPP case study #2 – GALAHAD

The next photonics PPP case is the GALAHAD project which targets the critical need for better glaucoma diagnostic systems.

Glaucoma is an age-related major cause of blindness. GALAHAD aims to develop a label free, compact and easy to operate high resolution diagnostic optical coherence tomography (OCT) system which will use submicron ultra-high resolution polarization sensitive OCT. A polarized laser will be used in order to improve the glaucoma screening process.

The project received funding from the Horizon 2020 framework.

The project consortium comprises 10 members:

- Several photonics technology businesses from the UK, Denmark
- Research institutes from Denmark and the UK
- A hospital foundation trust from the the UK
- The Universitat Politècnica de València from Spain
- The University of Münster from Germany

The system will drastically decrease false positive and false negative screening results which often occur in current solutions and reduce the number of patients suffering from glaucoma-related disability.

Figure 12 Photonics PPP – Galahad

4.6. Photonics PPP case study #3 – WaterSpy

The third photonics PPP case is WaterSpy.

WaterSpy project aims to develop water quality detection photonics technology suitable for inline, field measurements, operating in the 6-10µm region.

Currently, water utilities rely heavily on frequent sampling and laboratory analysis in order to acquire this information. For this situation to be improved, portable and high-performance devices for pervasive water quality monitoring are required.

Project received funding from the Horizon 2020 framework.

The project is being developed by 9 parties:

- Businesses from Switzerland, Italy, Greece, Poland
- Business innovation center from Cyprus
- Research center from Italy
- Universities in Greece, Austria, Germany

The developed technology will effectively contribute directly to increased health and safety of European and other citizens by:

- providing the capability to detect biological agents in the Water network
- assist all related stakeholders to reduce vulnerabilities to terrorism, prevent and prepare for terrorist attacks, minimize public health impacts and infrastructure damage, and enhance recovery from any attacks that may occur.

Figure 13 Photonics PPP – Waterspy

5. 5th-Generation Wireless Systems (5G)

This section describes the theory to be presented during the 5G webinar. It includes the theory on what the 5G market is and introduces the audience with successful PPP cases in the 5G market.

5.1. What is 5G

5G is the next wireless cellular communication standard, which is expected to transmit 1 gigabit of information per second – and perhaps as many as 10. The first generation, retroactively called 1G, was a fully analog system for transmitting voice. In contrast, 2G phones transmitted voice and data digitally. Subsequent generations, 3G in 2000 and 4G in 2010, made technical improvements that brought data rates up from 200 kilobits per second to hundreds of megabits per second. With 2020 approaching, 5G is expected to transmit 1 gigabit per second – and perhaps as many as 10.

Being able to send and receive that much data so quickly opens new opportunities for augmented and virtual reality systems, as well as automation. The new communication standard will help power the rise of IoT (internet of things) technology, which requires large amounts of data carried. This, in turn, will pave the way for a smarter and more connected world.

Currently, scientists cannot answer how exactly 5G technology will look like. However, the technologies that are emerging as the foundation of 5G include:

- **Millimeter waves.** Currently, mobile devices and electronics use specific radio waves – under 6 GHz. As more devices come online, mobile carriers have trouble fitting them in that radio wave spectrum. Therefore, scientists are experimenting with millimeter waves – radio waves that fall between 30 and 300 GHz. This would mean more bandwidth for all electronics users, however, these millimeter waves cannot travel well between buildings and other obstacles and are often absorbed by trees or rain. To mitigate this problem, the Small Cell technology is being developed.
- **Small cell.** Since millimeter waves have trouble travelling from transmission towers to the user and avoiding obstacles, thousands low power base stations, called Small Cell networks, would solve the problem. These base stations would be much closer together than current transmission towers and would create a so called trail around obstacles.
- **Massive MIMO.** MIMO stands for Multiple Input, Multiple Output. Current 4G transmission towers have about a dozen ports for antennas that handle the cellular traffic. Massive MIMO stations will be able to have about a hundred ports. This could increase the network's capacity by about 20 times compared to current technology. However, current antennas transmit radio waves to all directions at once and a drastic increase in transmission devices could cause massive interference with the signal. Therefore, Beamforming technology is necessary.
- **Beamforming.** This technology would allow a base station to transmit data in a focused stream to a specific user instead of in all directions at once. This prevents interference and is more efficient – stations could handle more incoming and outgoing data streams at once.
- **Full duplex.** Current transmission stations can only handle one action at a time – either transmitting or receiving data. Therefore, the signals might sometimes interfere. Full duplex would allow the incoming and outgoing streams to go around each other and travel to the addressee without interference.

5G technology is still in development and scientists cannot say how it will look eventually. One thing is known – it will be a new technological revolution that opens new doors not only in the communications, but in almost all sectors.

Figure 14 Evolution of wireless technologies

5.2. 5G applications in real life

Being able to send and receive that much data so quickly opens new opportunities for augmented and virtual reality systems, as well as automation of all kind of infrastructures. Figure 10 shows some use cases for 5G technology extracted from ERICSSON webpage⁴.

Figure 15 Real use cases for 5G - ERICSSON

Broadband and media everywhere

This use case shows how it will be possible to communicate in crowded or remote areas at high speed, thanks to a decrease in latency and the increase in data rates. Thanks to 5G, every mobile user will experience high-quality broadband service both upload and download.

Smart vehicles and transport

Sensors embedded in roads, railways, airfields and vehicles will communicate with each other through the 5G network. Ericsson is fully aware that this use case is focused on massive machine type communication and is working to ensure that the 5G network has the necessary high coverage and low power consumption.

Critical services and infrastructure control

5G brings high reliability and low latency required to control critical services and infrastructure. This unlocks new opportunities for public safety, government, city management and utility companies.

Critical control of remote devices

Ericsson's 5G network allows for remote control of heavy machinery. This opens the way for new possibilities such as increased efficiency and reduced cost or risk reduction in hazardous environments.

Human machine interaction

The high performance of 5G networks will make IoT more accessible by humans, to enhance the awareness of the context in which people live. Ericsson 5G system allows for the context awareness that allows you to fill the gap between people and IoT.

Sensors networks

5G technology will expand business opportunities through monitoring, tracking and automation capabilities on a large scale - from connected farms and agriculture to smart cities and buildings.

For instance, self-driving cars could communicate with each other, road signs, traffic signals, guard rails and other elements human drivers simply see. That would require an additional technical leap – reducing what is called “latency,” or the delay between when a signal is sent and when it’s received, to 1 millisecond. (If a network’s data rate is how wide a garden hose is, latency is how long it takes from the moment the spigot is turned on until water comes out the end.) It is this increase in bandwidth and decrease in latency what will dramatically increase the functionality that could be offered by low-power, massively distributed systems.

5.1. 5G-PPP initiative of the European Commission

The public-private 5G infrastructure association (PPP 5G) is a joint initiative of the European Commission and the European ICT industry (ICT manufacturers, telecommunications operators, service providers, SMEs and research institutions). The 5G-PPP launched its second phase in June 2017, with the kick-off of 21 new projects.

⁴ <https://www.ericsson.com/en/5g/use-cases>

The objective of the 5G-PPP is to provide solutions, architectures, technologies and standards for the ubiquitous next-generation communication infrastructures of the next decade, in order to ensure Europe's leadership in the specific areas in which Europe is strong or where there is potential to create new markets, such as smart cities, e-health, intelligent transport, education or entertainment. It will open "*a platform that will help us achieve our common goal of maintaining and reinforcing global technological leadership.*". Among the main challenges for the 5G Infrastructure PPP it is worth highlighting the following:

- Provides 1000 times greater wireless area capacity and more varied service capabilities compared to 2010
- Savings of up to 90% of energy per service rendered. The focus will be mainly on mobile communication networks, where the predominant energy consumption comes from the radio access network.
- Reduction of the average time of creation of services from 90 hours to 90 minutes
- Creation of a secure, reliable and reliable Internet with "zero perceived" downtime for the provision of services
- Facilitate very dense deployments of wireless communication links to connect more than 7 billion wireless devices that serve more than 7 billion people.
- Guarantee access to a wider range of services and applications at a lower cost for everyone and everywhere.

Figure 16 Main objectives of 5G-PPP (extracted from <https://5g-ppp.eu/>)

5.2. 5G PPP case study #1 – PHYLAWS

The first 5G PPP success cases is the project named PHYLAWS.

PHYLAWS stands for **PHYSical LAyer Wireless Security**

The main objective of the project is to design and prove efficiency of new privacy concepts for wireless communications that exploit propagation properties of radio channels.

PHYLAWS will investigate the new security approaches that are issued from information theory fundamentals and focus on the secrecy capacity of the propagation channel. These security approaches will be investigated for handsets and communications nodes that operate at the radio interface.

Project received funding from the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7)

The project is being developed by 5 partners:

- Businesses from Israel, France

- Imperial College in London
- Research Center from Finland

PHYLAWs' impact will be societal (more confidence, more privacy) and industrial (supporting European industry in developing and commercializing new security solutions).

Figure 17 5G-PPP: PHYLAWs

5.3. 5G PPP case study #2 – Flex5Gware

The second 5G PPP success case is Flex5Gware.

Flex5Gware project aims to address the improvement of the performance and the reduction of the energy footprint of the hardware and software platforms, on top of which all communications-related functionalities are implemented and executed. According to the project page, "Flex5Gware will adopt a holistic approach performing research and implementations on key building blocks of 5G (and cooperations among them) to provide versatile, flexible, reconfigurable, efficient operations for HW/SW platforms. The development of this concept entails many system design challenges that will be solved through disruptive technologies. E.g., analogue components to enable massive MIMO for mmWave, full duplex (simultaneous transmission and reception) for 5G waveforms, or reconfigurable SW architectures with interface abstractions for flexible control and management mechanisms across heterogeneous wireless devices and access networks."

The project received funding from the Horizon2020 framework

The project is being conducted by 17 partners:

- 5 large industries
- 3 SMEs
- 6 research institutions
- 3 universities

The project has a direct benefit to the European society linked to the improvements in the quality of service, increased number of applications and services, and has reduced cost of the future mobile networks.

Figure 18 5G-PPP: Flex5Gware

5.4. 5G PPP case study #3 – METIS II

The third 5G PPP case is METIS II which builds on the successful METIS project and will develop the overall 5G radio access network design and to provide the technical enablers needed for an efficient integration and use of the various 5G technologies and components currently developed.

METIS-II will provide the 5G collaboration framework within 5G-PPP for a common evaluation of 5G radio access network concepts and prepare concerted action towards regulatory and standardization bodies.

The project received funding from the Horizon2020 framework and is being developed by a consortium of 19 members:

- Large corporations from Sweden, Germany, China, Poland, Finland, France, the UK, Italy, USA
- Universities from Sweden, USA, Spain, Germany
- Research institutes from France, Taiwan, Spain

METIS-II will provide the 5G collaboration framework within 5G-PPP for a common evaluation of 5G radio access network concepts and prepare concerted action towards regulatory and standardization bodies.

Figure 19 5G-PPP: METIS II

6. SME Growth- Access to Finance

This webinar will be led by David Gill, Managing Director of St John’s Innovation Centre. David is a leading expert on access to finance and author of a number of publications on this topic. David previously ran and set-up the innovation & technology Unit at HSBC bank. He is currently a non-executive director of a crowdfunding business, SyndicateRoom Ltd and an active adviser to businesses seeking to secure finance.

Kirsten Masson, who will be presenting on the grants section, is a grant specialist and has supported many SMEs to access grant, business angel and VC finance. She has also been a grant assessor for a major national business grant programme.

6.1. Access to Finance Funding Ladder

▲ Funding Ladder

Slide 7: Landscape: Funding Ladder

Capital needs HIGH RISK

Exit IPO/Trade Sale

Expansion Capital

Bank Finance

“Real” Venture Capital

“Valley of Death”

LOW RISK

Maturity/time

Pre-seed SEED START-UP EARLY GROWTH SUSTAINED GROWTH

Friends Family Neighbors

Grants

Seed Hybrid Funds

Cor Investment Funds Business Angels Crowdfunding?

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Slide 8: The Most Important Source of Funding

customer زبون clienti 顧客 cwsmeriaid

müşteri clientes عميل زبون

kunde parokyano ग्राहक zákaznik

klient קלינט client 客戶 klienci

8

Slide 9: Different Firms, Different Profiles...

Bank balance £

Time

Technology firm

- Large investment required
- Late breakeven
- Huge upside (Apple, Google)

Consulting firm

- Low investment required
- Early breakeven
- Modest upside

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Slide 10: Financing- The Essentials

- You won’t get money just because you need it
- You must be “funding-ready”
- Your finances (or financial projections) must look good
- Right source at the right time with the right story

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The access to finance funding ladder will help participants to understand the different types of finance available and those they are likely to need at different stages of growth. An understanding of the impact the nature of the technology may have on variances to this model will be explained.

The key types of funding that will be outlined are grants, business angel investment, VC funds and debt finance. There will also be content on alternative sources of finance including crowdfunding and peer to peer lending. It will be made clear that revenues are the major source of funding required for any business to be successful and that the sooner these can be generated the better. This therefore needs to be taken into consideration when developing business models.

This content can be flexed following input from participant feedback from workshops to ensure that it is relevant and focused on the priorities outlined by the target audience.

6.2. Grants

An outline of the different types of grants available for enterprises will be provided. This will include a wide range of European grants, for example Eurostars, FET open, Fast Track to Innovation, SME instrument and ESIF funds. Eligibility criteria, partnership opportunities and benefits will be detailed. Links to the individual grant funds will be made available at the end of the webinar. Support organisations who can offer assistance will also be referenced.

1. GRANTS

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What are Business Grants for?

In Europe, business grants are mainly available for:

- Technology R&D projects and commercialisation
- Social enterprises
- Assisted Areas

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Some Pros & Cons of Grant Funding

Some good things

1. They can provide cash for early stage, risky ventures
2. Unlike debt, need not be repaid (except in default)
3. Unlike equity, founders don't have to sell shares
4. They can help to persuade equity investors
5. They can support collaboration with others

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Some Pros & Cons of Grant Funding

Some not so good things

1. Most schemes may not suit your business
2. Applying takes precious time and effort
3. Mostly available for early-stage projects
4. Strict spending and reporting rules
5. For some grants costs reimbursed in arrears
6. Most require match funding

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How to Approach Grant Funding

The wrong way
"I've heard there's a grant available – what do I need to do to get it?"

The right way
"I know what I want to do and how to do it, now let's see if there is a scheme that aligns well with my plans?"

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European Grant Funding

EIC- European Innovation Council: "supports top-class innovators, entrepreneurs, small companies and scientists with bright ideas and the ambition to scale up internationally."

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/eic/index.cfm>

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SME Instrument

The SME Instrument is for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs – including start-ups) with a radical innovation that can disrupt established value networks and markets.

There are two types of grants:

- concept and feasibility grants of €50,000 to assess the viability of an innovation
- demonstration, testing, piloting and scaling grants of up to €2.5 million with a 70% co-financing rate

Bespoke coaching support provided with both grants

<http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/sme-instrument>

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SME Instrument Client Case Study

Top Tip:

- Read the guidance before beginning
- Focus on the commercial benefit for the EU if they fund your project
- Get external critique
- Get in touch with your SME Instrument National Contact Point (NCP) or local Enterprise Europe Network Team (EEN)
- Persevere- Don't give up!

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Fast Track to Innovation (FTI)

For more mature ground-breaking technologies, concepts and business models which are close to market

Proposals must come from consortia of 3 to 5 legal entities who want to see quick market uptake of new technologies. Grants of up to €3 million may be awarded

- For-profit entities will receive 70% co-financing
- Not-for-profit entities will receive 100% co-financing

<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/101020-ep-01on-fast-track-innovation>

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Future Enabling Technologies (FET Open)

- FET Open offers grants circa €3 million to promote collaborative, inter-disciplinary research and innovation on future and emerging technologies
- For consortia of at least 3 entities
- FET Innovation Launchpad grants of up to €100,000 for short individual or collaborative actions to help turn the results of FET Open projects into innovations

<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/101020-ep-01on-fet-open>

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European Structural and Investment Funds

Over half of EU funding is channelled through the 5 European structural and investment funds (ESIF).

The ESIF mainly focus on 5 areas:

- Research and innovation
- Digital technologies
- Supporting the low-carbon economy
- Sustainable management of natural resources
- Small businesses

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Support Programmes

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Start-up Europe Programmes

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An SME instrument successful case study, ANB Sensors, will be presented to illustrate this grant award. This business was developed from a research project and has produced disruptive sensor technology for water monitoring. They have successfully secured phase 1 and phase 2 SME instrument funding and have been supported by being connected to the available business support infrastructure. They are linking with key global players in their industry and have benefitted significantly from the commercialisation support provided.

Support organisations who can offer assistance will also be referenced.

6.3. Business Angels & VC Funds

The webinar will outline the differences between Business Angels and Venture Capital funds. Content will also be provided on what Angels and VCs look for when considering investment so that participants have a better understanding of how to approach investors and how to create a quality pitch deck to garner interest in their technology.

Links to European Business Angel Networks will be provided.

2. Business Angels & VC Funds

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Two Very Different Sources of Equity Finance

Business Angels
Individuals or syndicates with flexibility to support any sector/location

Venture Capital Funds
Often acting on behalf of institutions, looking for close/at market technologies which will deliver big exits in short time frames

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Definition of a Business Angel

"An individual, acting alone or in a formal or informal syndicate, who invests his or her own money directly in an unquoted business in which there is no family connection and who, after making the investment, takes an active involvement in the business, for example, as an advisor or member of the board of directors."

Prof Colin Mason and Prof Richard Harrison, 2007

Angels currently invest >3x more in early-stage than VCs

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Due Diligence: What Angels Look For

- Team, Product, Market, Sector, Profits, Exit...
- Investors back people with a range of abilities: fill gaps
- Exceptional growth prospects, Sector, timing
- Protection – not just IPI Know-how, first-mover gains
- Stage: more than just an idea; prove yourself first
- Explain business model: where you fit, how you make €€€
- Investment readiness of the business ... and the people
- Valuation now and at exit
- What happens when you need more money??

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Where Angels & VC Funds Are Different

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Angels manage their own money (syndicates possible) ○ Angels can choose any sector, location... ○ Angels can choose anything attractive/interesting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ VCs are hired hands, often acting for institutions ○ VCs have constitution and investment committee ○ VCs bonus driven, need big exits/short time frames
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Angel Tax Breaks

- Numerous international examples
 - Many US states, Ireland, France
- Set investment against income tax liability and/or provide capital gains incentives
- Theory: trade off uncertainty for tax benefit
- UK experience:
 - Angels = 3x venture funding at early stage
 - 82% of angels used tax schemes
 - 57% of investments made under tax schemes

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European Business Angel Networks

The European Trade Association for Business Angels, Seed Funds and Early Stage Market Players

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Corporate Investment

- Many large corporations have investment funds
 - Act like VCs: ring-fenced activity, strong sector focus
 - Conflicts of interest? Find at least 2?
 - Will have a clear process and 'rules'
- Some SMEs may act like private investors
 - Directors/shareholders interested in opportunities they understand and that have synergy with their business

Finding corporate funds is easy, finding strategic interest takes initiative

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6.4. Valuation

The webinar will outline valuation methodologies to enhance participants understanding of valuation calculations so that they are able to create this for their enterprise. Factors that influence valuations including: market accessibility, time to market, market size, market need, costs, team, novelty and defensibility will be highlighted and explained.

Valuation

The valuation of your business is critical: a high 1st round price may limit your ability to attract future investors

BUT ENTREPRENEURS SAY:
 "I don't want to give up more than 50%"
 "I want to give away as little as possible"

With equity, you are not GIVING anything.
 You are SELLING, and you must negotiate the right price

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Valuing Technology Firms...

"Valuing technology projects is more of an art than a science."
 "Most approaches are based on tools used to value more tangible assets."
 "Managers often complain that standard tools such as Discounted Cash Flow and Net Present Value are not suited to the uncertainties of technology management."

"Valuing and Selecting Technology Projects"
 Institute for Manufacturing, University of Cambridge

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In theory you can calculate a technology's value...

...but uncertainties in the input variables lead to uncertainties in the valuation. Big ones....

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6.5. Banks vs Equity Investment

Difference between debt finance and equity will be demonstrated and participants will have a better understanding of likely success and failure rates of investment propositions. A quality business plan model will be set out with the do's and don'ts for content creation to enable participants to have a clear understanding of what is required to lever initial interest and ultimately to secure finance.

3. Banks vs Equity Investors

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Equity Investors (money for shares)

High risk investors
 High returns required: 5-10x money invested, because:

Of 10 investments:
 ○ 3 will fail
 ○ 4 will be walking wounded
 ○ Of the other 3, only 1 or 2 will star

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Business Plans for Equity Providers

- An outstanding 2-3 page executive summary
- The market opportunity
- Product/technology and competitive analysis
- The business model
- The management team
- Keep it short; use appendices for bigger items

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The Executive Summary

- A critical 'hook' for funders
- 2 page overview that excites interest
- Help readers to understand your proposal
- Get an independent view (honest friends)
- Don't approach investors until it is right

Think of it as your "elevator pitch"

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An insight into dilution of ownership following investment rounds will also be highlighted.

Reference to alternative sources of fund raising e.g. crowd funding, peer-to-peer lending will be included along with an overview of alternative finance volume figures across Europe.

6.6. Managing the Money

4. Managing the money

IN TERMS OF MONEY

WE HAVE NO MONEY.

SPEND SAVE

money

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Burn Rate

Burn rate = negative cash flow

OR: how soon you exhaust shareholder capital

THEN: new funding, make profits, close down...

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Financial Statements

- Balance sheet
- Profit & Loss Account / Income statement
- Cash Flow
- (statement of changes in equity)
- All are linked to each other

For start-up firms, Cash Flow is THE key item

- Management/board to check solvency
- Identify when out-of-cash looming

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An overview of the importance of financial management and the key pieces of financial data required will be highlighted. These will include balance sheet, profit and loss, income statement, cash flow.

Cash burn rate and break-even points will be demonstrated so that participants have a better knowledge of the financials they need to create and monitor. This will also support the preparation of financials as part of business planning and pitch deck preparation.

6.7. Case Studies

Illustrated cases will be provided throughout the webinar to highlight successful and unsuccessful fundraising examples and lessons learnt. The cases will give participants insights into the best approaches to securing investment and timings and a clear understanding of the preparation required to be successful.

At the end the webinar participants will be signposted to suitable reading materials for further learning. In addition, links to the grant funds referenced and organisations that offer further support will be provided.

7. SME Growth- The Commercialisation Journey

To be present by David Gill and Uday Phadke.

David is the Managing Director of St John's Innovation Centre. David is a leading expert on access to finance and author of a number of publications on this topic. David previously ran and set-up the innovation & technology Unit at HSBC bank. He is currently a non-executive director of a crowdfunding business, SyndicateRoom Ltd and an active adviser to businesses seeking to secure finance.

Uday's career over the last thirty-five years has spanned three distinct but related areas: commercial businesses enabled by science and technology; academic research and teaching in technology and business; and the design and promotion of national and international innovation initiatives.

He has been Chief Executive of Cartezia the Cambridge-based technology business builder since 1997. He was an Entrepreneur in Residence at the Judge Business School at Cambridge University from 2011 to 2016. He has worked extensively across Europe, Asia and North America, including Technology Strategy Programmes for the EU Framework Programme, the Conference Board in the United States and Innovation Programmes in India for Council of Scientific and Industrial Research.

Uday is an author of a number of books including '*Camels, Tigers & Unicorns: Rethinking science and technology-enabled innovation*' and '*The Scale-up Manual*' will be published in June 2018.

7.1. The Commercialisation Journey and Triple Chasm Model

1. The Building Blocks

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Commercialisation Journey

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The Scale-Up Manual

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The Triple Chasm Model

- The early stages of growth take a lot longer than most perceive
- Typically, half-way through the product journey, cumulative customer penetration will have reached about 10% of the maximum number of customers

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Approach to Estimating Maturity

Readiness Level from exploitation perspective	
0	Research in progress
1	Validated Research: start concept definition
2	Initial Concept Defined
3	Working Prototype or Demonstrator
Chasm I	
4	Product or Service Testing and Concept Refinement
5	Proven Product or Service
6	Deployment with early customers in real commercial environment
Chasm II	
7	Product or service ready for testing in real user environment
8	Refinement of Product or service
9	Ready for Commercial Deployment with Real Customers
Chasm III	

Adapted from NASA TRL Approach

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An overview of the commercialisation journey which looks at an innovation from idea to maturity. This outlines the 3 Chasms (risk areas) that can affect different firms as they grow. This is used to help characterise growth that is interrupted by the 3 chasms where cumulative customer growth stalls. This methodology uses technology readiness levels to estimate commercialisation maturity. This webinar aims to simplify the model so that individuals are aware of and can equip themselves to navigate potential chasms along their commercialisation journey.

The triple chasm model illustrates that the early part of the commercialisation journey may take much longer than envisaged. The webinar will highlight different barriers to growth.

7.2. Drivers for Commercialisation

The drivers are what influences a firm’s commercialisation trajectory. The Webinar helps participants to understand what the drivers are, whether the driver is internal, external or joint and how to maximise their positive impact to fuel growth and avoid chasms. The drivers include:

- Market spaces
- Propositions framing
- Competition & Regulation
- Customer definition
- Marketing and sales commercialisation strategy
- Business model
- Technology development
- Intellectual Property
- Product & service consolidation
- Manufacturing & deployment
- Talent leadership & culture
- Funding & investment.

Participants will also be able to understand the relevance of each of these drivers along the growth journey. The driver relevance will be associated to their technology readiness so that participants can understand the what drivers will be influencing them at a given point.

Drivers for Commercialisation

The 12 Drivers that shape the commercialisation journey are split into 3 sections:

Internal Joint External

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External Drivers That Influence Growth

1. Market Spaces
2. Proposition Framing, Competition & Regulation
3. Customer Definition
4. Distribution Marketing & Sales

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Joint Drivers

1. Commercialisation Strategy
2. Business Model

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Internal Drivers that Influence Growth

1. Technology Development
2. IP Management
3. Product & Service Consolidation
4. Manufacturing & Deployment
5. Talent Leadership & Culture
6. Funding & Investment

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Driver relevance along the growth journey

Section of Drivers	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Market Spaces													
Proposition Framing													
Customer Definition													
Distribution, Marketing & Sales													
Commercialisation Strategy													
Business Models													
Tech, Ops & Commercial Development													
Product and Service Dev. & Support													
Manufacturing & Deployment													
IP Management													
Talent Leadership and Culture													
Funding & Investment													

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7.3. Key Issues

Key issues

Make something people need, make something people want
(and will pay for)

- Know your market space
 - Understand your competitors
 - See future trends
- Does the technology deliver?
- IP management- Protecting your ideas, where feasible
 - Not just patent it is also copyright, design, knowhow and trademarks

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Key issues (cont.)

- Talent, leadership and culture
 - Do you have the right team?
 - Do you have any skill gaps?
- What are your funding needs? Do you have sufficient funds to take you to launch?
 - What is your burn rate?
 - When will you reach break even

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Chasm 2: WARNING!!

ALL DRIVERS MATTER

Greatest risk of failure

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7 Marketing P's

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The key issues are outlined for our target audience. This will be heavily weighted towards very early stage business so there will be a focus on the drivers most affecting them and how to overcome chasm 1. The 3 key drivers to address to overcome chasm 1 are market space for the proposition, technology development and Intellectual Property management.

Chasm 2 is when all 12 drivers are in play. By this point there is expected to be an emphasis shift from technology management to product management. Participants will be provided with practical advice as to how best to address all drivers to minimise the risk of chasm 2 and maximise the commercialisation benefits.

This will also help participants to understand how their business priorities may change as they progress through the commercialisation journey.

7.4. Case Study 1- Global Business

Case study 1 focuses on a global business that successfully navigated the commercialisation journey. It shows the opportunity, vision and the approach/solution to the chasm. The business created a digital imaging platform and tools for the media industry.

Case Study 1

Case study: Global Business that has successfully overcome barriers to growth and how they navigated the 3 chasms.

Digital Imaging & Tools for the media industry

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Crossing Chasm 1

Opportunity: Spotted a market opportunity, defined target customers and framed proposition

Vision: Image based content and services to SMEs

Approach to chasm: Technology development and deployment of prototype. IP registration

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Chasm 1:

Opportunity: As the volume of web-based content grew dramatically in the late 1990s the firm recognised the opportunity to provide imagery to media and advertising players building their own web-sites

Vision: Provision of image-based content and services to SME's and digital media entrepreneurs based on a new low-cost business model

Approach: The approach adopted was to create indexable image databases, to build image banks and allow customers to access and buy content using online tools

Solution: Initial setup- acquisition of image assets, built new indexing system for searchable images, introduced new technology for watermarking images, produced a prototype for pilot.

Crossing Chasm 2

- Multiple iterations of technology platform to ensure it was stable.
- Provision of 'royalty free' images and image handling tools to publishers, media agencies and web developers

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Crossing Chasm 2 (cont.)

- Built an integrated service platform
- Disruptive use of copyright
- Tested with customers in media and advertising industry
- Experimented with business model to ensure margin generation
- Talent management- built a strong and diverse team.
- Defined clear commercialisation strategy

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Chasm 2:

The business extended the technology beyond the prototype and built the full-service platform which was deployed with the customer. Multiple iterations were released until the platform was stable. The business experimented with different business models until they found one that provided robustness, sustainability and strong margins.

The **Key Drivers** at this stage were:

External Drivers: Widen and deepen understanding and interaction with customers (customer definition & sales).

Internal Drivers: Managing human talent.

Joint Drivers: Defining a clear commercialisation strategy and focusing on execution. Adoption of a new business model, called **royalty-free** which reversed previous commercial logic and was highly innovative.

Crossing Chasm 3

Opportunity: Global scale;

- Radically increased their marketing space
- Acquisition of firms with significant image assets
- Land grab strategy- captured new geographical territory facilitated by multiple acquisitions
- Refined the offering to increase the value to customers
- Introduced new market leading technology
- Improved delivery and customisation to individual needs
- Aligning senior management team with the growth strategy
- Adjustment to business model to maximise profit
- Leveraged networks
- Secured sufficient funding for global scale

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Chasm 3:

Significant ramping up of revenues to cross Chasm 3 consisted of 3 steps:

- Systematic acquisition of a range of companies to provide global coverage, wider sets of imagery and new image manipulation tools
- Ensuring the provision of all these assets through a single branded access portal
- Structure marketing and sales programme to ensure an active presence in all key geographies and market segments

The **Key Drivers** at this stage were:

External Drivers: Widening the proposition, distribution, marketing & sales with the emphasis on pace; the view was to sign up many deals quickly and then fine tune based on experience- classic land-grab approach

Internal Driver: Securing top quality executive team and ensuring they had the right strengths to take forward a fast scaling business.

Joint Drivers: Adjustments to the business model to reflect the wider customer base and value proposition. Focus on minimising the impact of competitors.

7.5. Case Study 2

Case 2- Business That Fell Into a Chasm

- Management team failed to plan strategy
- Didn't take notice of industry trends
- Burn rate exceeded revenues
- Team members became disillusioned
- Team grew too quickly

Blockbuster- An example of a scaling business which collapsed at Chasm 3.

At the height of their success Blockbuster employed 50,000 staff and the business was worth over \$8bn. However, by 2012 the business had collapsed. Reasons why;

External Drivers

They had minimal engagement/feedback with their customers

They were not aware of what their competitors were doing

They failed to keep up to date with market trends

Internal Drivers

The management team did not have clarity over the business proposition- entertainment or retail offering.

They failed to review their business model

Joint Drivers

They were offered the opportunity of a partnership with Netflix. However, they did not capitalise on this and Netflix is not worth over \$28bn.

Lessons learnt – no matter the size or the success of the business the drivers are always key and should be kept under constant review.

7.6. Case Study 3

Case Study 3

Early Stage business- successfully navigated the Chasms

Points to make;

- Pivoting technology
- Pivoting business model to achieve scalable revenues
- Listening to customer feedback
- Understanding a building a customer base
- Maximising IP value
- Building a successful team

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Case Study 3

Cambridge University Spin Out ICT company that produced holographic laser projectors. The technology was strong - technology peers liked it. The founders were heavily influenced by their immediate circle – investors

liked it and secured one of the largest funding rounds in the sector. Initial customer testing was positive but was a very narrow band of interest – early adopters only.

They crossed chasm 1 with a product that worked and a small customer base. They had a management team and investment in place. However, product market penetration was weak sales were low. The product failed to gain significant commercial traction. Cash became problematic, burn rate was fast due to the size of the team and further investment was difficult. The company growth stalled and debt became an issue.

To cross chasm 2 the company focused on addressing the following drivers;

External

Market spaces – Industry trends – spotting gaps and how their technology could address these, new market opportunities explored – decided to be more focused and concentrate on education and training

Proposition Framing- a better understanding of the market opportunity for their product

Customer definition – sought feedback from a wider range of people including current customers and potential pipeline. What they liked/didn't like and what they would pay for

Distribution Marketing & Sales- Distributors/resellers secured, US office established

Internal

Technology Development & Contingent Deployment- Created minimum viable production which is a pivot of the original product – camera that takes interactive pictures – real time imagery with no distortion, multiple platform opportunities

Manufacturing & Deployment- simplified production methods

Talent Leadership & Culture- Revamped the management team to bring in missing skills and to remove any duplication

IP Management- IP registered and secured

Funding & Investment – venture capitalist came on board once the value proposition of the business was clear and they had got the right management team on place

Joint drivers

Commercialisation strategy in place

Business Model- Revised investment strategy in place and secured in line with vision

The company now has a turnover in excess of £10m and is scaling fast in the UK, Europe and US. They continue to keep all drivers under review to ensure they are well placed to deliver their strategic vision and financial forecasts.

8. Conclusions

All 4 webinars aim to equip researchers with knowledge on how to commercialize their innovations. The webinars support with finding and securing the right finance, securing private public partnerships and understanding the commercialization journey. The webinars will be recorded and the slides circulated to participants to maximise take up and the learnings. Any additional issues arising from the Q&A sessions will be written up and added to the slide decks before circulating to ensure they are captured for the participants.

We will continue to update the materials on the basis of feedback given by participants attending the MERLIN ICT workshop programs to ensure that it remains relevant, up-to-date and tailored to the needs of participants.